

Informed Consent Form (ICF)

Exploring the Use of AI Assistants for UML Diagram Modeling in Classroom Activities

1. Introduction and Purpose of the Study

You are being invited to participate in a study conducted by the Software Engineering Research Group at the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS).

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the benefits and challenges encountered by students when manually creating UML Activity Diagrams based on use case descriptions, as well as to compare the quality and accuracy of these diagrams with versions automatically generated by the LucidChart GPT tool.

This experiment seeks to generate relevant insights into how artificial intelligence tools can transform teaching and learning practices in Software Engineering, particularly in supporting modeling, requirements specification, and team collaboration.

The results may contribute to advancements both in academic research and professional practice.

2. Voluntary Participation

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may refuse to participate or withdraw at any time, without providing any justification and without any loss of rights or penalties. You may also choose not to answer any question that makes you feel uncomfortable.

3. Confidentiality and Data Protection

All responses will be treated anonymously. No personally identifiable information (such as name, email, company, or IP address) will be collected.

The data will be securely stored in password-protected files accessible only to the research team. The results may be published in academic papers, conference proceedings, or reports, always in aggregated form, without identifying individual participants.

The data may also be reused in future research related to this topic, while fully preserving anonymity.

4. Potential Risks

The risks associated with participating in this study are minimal and similar to those found in typical academic activities. There may be mild discomfort when reflecting on challenges or limitations during the modeling process. If this occurs, you may stop or skip any question.

5. Potential Benefits

There are no direct financial benefits for participating. You may benefit personally by reflecting on your own modeling practices and strategies.

Indirectly, your participation will contribute to improving the understanding of how AI and language models can be responsibly integrated into the software development process.

6. Duration

The questionnaire will take approximately 10 to 15 minutes to complete.

7. Right to information and access to results

You may request additional information about the study at any time.

After the study is completed, a summary of the findings may be made available upon request.

8. Research team contact information

If you have any questions or concerns about this study, please contact:

Email: leticia.machado@inf.ufrgs.br

9. Consent Statement

By proceeding to the questionnaire, you confirm that:

- You are 18 years of age or older;
- You have read and understood the information provided above;
- You voluntarily agree to participate in this study.